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GEO-STUDIES FORUM

An International Journal of Environmental and Policy Issues

**Department of Geography and Environmental Management, Faculty of Social Sciences,
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SPATIO-TEMPORAL ANALYSIS OF LAND USE/LAND COVER CHANGES (LULCC) IN EFON LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, EKITI STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract: *The earth's surface is being significantly altered by human activities resulting in an observable pattern of change in the Land Use Land Cover (LULC). The study examined Land Use and Land Cover Change (LULCC) pattern in Efon Local Government Area of Ekiti State, Nigeria over a period of thirty-six years (1985 and 2021), using remotely sensed satellite imageries and geospatial techniques and, covering four epochs. Five Land Use and Land Cover classes including, Built Up Areas (BU), Barren Land (BL), Forest Land (FL), Agricultural Land (AL) and Range Land (RL) were identified based on USGS/Anderson's classification model with Efon Alaaye being the only town and headquarter of the Local Government. Landsat 5 TM, Landsat 7 ETM+ and Landsat 8 OLI and TIRS images were acquired from United States Geological Survey (USGS) Earth Resources Observation and Science (EROS) for the supervised digital image classification using Arc GIS 10.8, OpenStreetMap (OSM) and Microsoft Excel. The results showed that between 1985 to 2021, Built Up Area (BU) increased by 60.88% from 311 to 795 hectares. There was decline in Forest Land (FL) by 26.63% from 5,635 to 4,134 hectares and Range Land (RL) by 7.90% from 8,9436 to 7,769 hectares but increase in Agricultural Land (AL) by 58.87% from 866 to 2,106 hectares and Barren Land (BL) by 14.94% from 2,527 to 2971 hectares. The creation of the Local Government Area in 1996 had remarkable effect on the growth of Built-Up Area (BU), Barren Land (BL) and Agricultural Land (AL), hence the utilization of Forest Land (FL) and Range Land (RL). The study recommended the need for continuous collection, analysis, interpretation and updating of data in the area for future development planning.*

Keywords: Land Satellite (Landsat); Land Use Land Cover (LULC); Remote Sensing (RS); United States Geological Survey (USGS)

INTRODUCTION

According to Bryant, Nielsen and Tangle (1997), Just one fifth of the world's original forest cover remains in large undisturbed tracts today, and the cutting has accelerated: about 16 million hectares are cut or burnt each year. The earth's surface is being significantly altered by human activities, and man's presence on the planet and his land use practices have had a profound impact on the natural environment, resulting in an observable pattern of change in the Land Use Land Cover (LULC) over time, ranging from the initial conversion of natural forest into cropland to the ongoing management of

grassland (Meyer, 1995). In this regard, about 400,000 hectares of vegetation cover are lost annually in the process worldwide (Adesina, Siyanbola, Oketola, Pelemo and Ojo, 1999; Balogun, Adeyewa, Balogun and Morakinyo, 2011). In the tropics, more than 55% of new agricultural land was at the expense of intact forests, while 28% was associated with disturbed forests from 1980–2000 (Gibbs, Ruesch, Achard, Clayton, Holmgren, Ramankutty and Foley, 2010).

Nigeria has the world's highest deforestation rate of primary forests according to revised deforestation figures from the Food and

Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO, 2005). Between 2000 and 2005, the country lost 55.7 percent of its primary forests, that is, forests with no visible signs of past or present human activity (FAO, 2005). FAO (2010) reported that the rate of deforestation in Nigeria between 1990 and 2010 was averagely 409,650 hectares or 2.38% per year.

In view of its impact on a wide variety of socio-economic and ecological processes (Verburg, Chen, Soepboer and Veeldkamp, 2000; Desanker, Frost, Justice and Scholes, 1997) that collectively affect global environmental change and the biosphere, LULCC is at the centre of environmental processes, environmental change, and environmental management. Land use and land cover change (LULCC) assessments serve a crucial role in identifying developing spatial patterns and the general direction of land degradation, land fragmentation, declining agricultural productivity, rural impoverishment and depopulation, and environmentally-induced movements of people (Verburg et al., 2000).

The ecological and developmental effects of land use change throughout time can only be fully understood by studying land use dynamics. This means that mapping land use and detecting changes in land use are useful data points to take into account for formulating and enforcing policy responses (Fasona and Omojola, 2005). Concerning the root causes, there is no one explanation since LULCC, are influenced by a wide variety of factors that work in both space and time. While the precise interplay of elements like population/income, technology, politics/society/economics/culture, and so on may vary from one region to the next, it is safe to say that there are certain universal constants at work (Lambin, Geist and Lepers, 2003). On the consequences of LULCC driven by

agriculture, urbanization, and deforestation, several researchers have focused on their adverse effects on ecology of the area and vegetation causing environmental degradation, including biodiversity loss, soil erosion, and disrupted hydrological cycles (Martinuzzi, Gouyld and Gonzalez, 2007; Sudhira, Ramachandra and Jagadish, 2004).

Several researches have shown that unplanned changes of land use due to urbanisation have become a major problem (Balogun, Adeyewa, Balogun and Morakinyo, 2011; Zhao, Dickson and Tian, 2004). LULCC are the major sources of habitat loss, ecosystem alterations and biodiversity changes in forest dominated landscapes. Land cover change resulting from human land uses represents a major source and a major element of global environmental change (Turner, Meyer and Skole, 1994; Ramachandra, Bharath and Durgappa, 2012). Land use change can consequently lead to environmental degradation, such as distortions of ecosystem health, environmental pollution, deforestation, erosion and change in stream flow to mention but a few. Land use change in areas such as forests, farmlands and around waterways are being driven by the need to provide food, shelter, fibre and water for more than seven billion people of the world (Foley, DeFries, Asner, Barford, Bonan, Carpenter, Chapin, Coe, Daily, Gibbs, Helkowski, Holloway, Howard, Kucharik, Monfreda, Patz, Prentice, Ramankutty and Snyder, 2005).

Since the creation of the Local Government in 1996 but first as Native Authority in 1981, Efon has undergone population growth, expansion, and developmental activities, resulting in land use modification. The rising demographic pressure and the human activities that go along with it, which have caused severe environmental stress and ecological instability, have made it necessary to pay more attention to the management of

natural resources in recent years. The results of the natural and socio-economic elements that affect land use and land cover in the local government area need a thorough examination of the causes, methods, and pace of Land Use and Land Cover Change. Therefore, the purpose of this study was to map out the status of land use and land cover of the local government area between 1985 and 2021, with a view to analyze the changes that have taken place in this area over a 36 years period, using remotely sensed satellite imagery. The specific objectives were to: identify the various LULC types and locations; determine the trend and magnitude of LULCC; examine the major drivers of LULCC; assess the implications of the LULCC observed for planning purposes and thereafter make appropriate recommendations.

STUDY AREA

The study area is Efon Local Government Area, Ekiti State, Nigeria (Figure 1). The headquarter of the Local Government Area is

Efon Alaaye, being the only town. It consists of many villages including: Oro, Obake, Iwaji, Etisun, Abeta, Agboro, Aladura, Alagba, Mesan, Alawaye, Araromi, Ido-Ajgunle, Igbo-Aba, Irunshi, Ita Awure, Ita Ido, Iwaji, Oba Ayetoro, Obake, Oke Agemo, Oko Adagba, Orisunbare and Oro (Nigeria Directory and Search Engine, 2016). The Local Government headquarter is located at latitude 7° 39'23''North of the equator and 4°55'20'' East of the Greenwich meridian (Mindat.org, 2024).

According to the website of Ekiti State (2025), the landscape and topography are hilly and mountainous while the climate is tropical with two major seasons, the raining and dry seasons. The area is blessed with well aerated soil that is good for arable farming and supports the raising of livestock.

Figure 1: Map of Ekiti State, Nigeria showing the location of Efon Local Government Area

Source: Image Analysis of Landsat Satellite Imagery, 2026.

METHODOLOGY

DATA DESCRIPTION

The study classification was based on the United States Geological Surveys Anderson’s

Land Use and Land Cover Classification System for use with Remote Sensor Data Scheme at Level I. Details of the data type, sources and characteristics is presented in Table 1

Table 1: Data Types, Sources and Characteristics

S/N	Sensor/Data Type	Capture Date	Spatial Resolution/Scale	Spectral Resolution
1.	Landsat 5 Thematic Map (TM)	11/12/1984	30m	7 Bands
2.	Landsat 7 Enhanced Thematic Map Plus (ETM+)	13/11/2000	30m	8 Bands
3.	Landsat-8 OLI and TIRS sensors	17/12/2015	30m	11Bands
4.	Landsat-8 OLI and TIRS	12/11/2020	30m	11Bands

Source: USGS Earth Resources Observation and Science Centre (2025), Field Survey 2025

DATA COLLECTION

Chrome based satellite browser was used for internet access. The study employed secondary data, remotely sensed Landsat satellite imageries covering thirty-six years period, obtained through the United States Geological Survey (USGS) Earth Resources Observation and Science (EROS) web services. To analyse temporal changes in Land Use and Land Cover (LULC), images from four distinct years (1985, 2000, 2015, and 2021) with minimal scan lines were carefully selected and downloaded.

To ensure seasonal consistency and comparability across the datasets, images with about 10% cloud cover, captured during fairly dry months of November and December, were chosen. Different Landsat missions were utilized based on the image availability for each period: Landsat 5 Thematic Mapper (TM) for 1985 and 2000; Landsat 7 Enhanced Thematic Mapper Plus (ETM+) for 2015; Landsat 8 Operational Land Imager (OLI) and Thermal Infrared Sensor (TIRS) for 2021. The downloaded imageries already georeferenced to projection system Universal Traverse Mercator (UTM), zone 31N with datum WGS 84 were then imported into ArcGIS 10.8 for the various stages of processing.

DATA PROCESSING

To improve the quality and alignment of the satellite data, rigorous preprocessing was conducted through the following steps:

Radiometric correction: This process involved converting raw Digital Numbers (DNs) into Top of Atmosphere (TOA) reflectance values. This step was essential to eliminate sensor noise and atmospheric effects, ensuring uniform radiometric response across all image datasets.

Geometric Correction: Using a Digital Elevation Model (DEM), geometric

correction was performed to align the imagery spatially, correcting for terrain-induced distortions and enhancing the spatial fidelity of the data across different years.

Image Sub-setting (Clipping): The satellite images were clipped using shapefiles delineating the boundary of the Local Government Area. These shapefiles were downloaded from OpenStreetMap (OSM) and ensured that only relevant spatial extents were analysed.

Band Composition and Visualization: A 5-4-3 band combination (Near Infrared, Red, and Green) was used to create False-Color Composite (FCC) images. These FCCs enhanced the visual distinction between vegetation, water bodies, built-up areas, and bare surfaces, aiding in better photo-interpretation and supervised classification.

CLASSIFICATION

A supervised classification technique was employed using Map 10.8. Training samples representing known land cover classes (built-up areas, barren, forest and agriculture) were manually digitized from the composite imagery.

These samples were used to create a signature file, which informed the Maximum Likelihood Classification (MLC) algorithm—an advanced statistical method that assigns pixels to the most probable land cover class based on their spectral similarity.

After classification, the resulting raster datasets were converted into vector (polygon) format, allowing for precise calculation of land cover areas for each class and each year.

A total of 4 thematic maps, each representing a period, were generated to showcase LULC distribution. Final map layouts were enhanced using standard cartographic elements (legend,

north arrow, scale bar, and title) in ArcMap 10.8's Layout View.

Three different satellite imageries acquired in 1985, 2000, 2015 and 2021, within the same period, were classified to see the land use and land cover transformation of Efon Local Government Area from 1985 to 2021.

The results of the local government area were presented with the aid of maps and tables to: identify the various land use and land cover types and locations; determine the trend and magnitude of LULCC; examine the major drivers of LULCC; and assess the implications of LULCC observed for planning purposes.

ACCURACY ASSESSMENT

To validate the classification results and ensure reliability: sample points were generated and compared with the reference

composite imagery to assess classification performance.

A confusion matrix (error matrix) was produced in ArcMap, quantifying the accuracy of each land cover class by comparing the classified data against known ground truth. The matrix yielded key metrics such as overall accuracy, user's accuracy, producer's accuracy, and the Kappa coefficient, which were exported into Microsoft Excel for further interpretation and reporting.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The five main types of land use and land cover discovered included Built Up Areas (BU), Barren Land (BL), Forest Land (FL), Agricultural Land (AL) and Range Land (RL). Each category is represented by a different colour based on USGS/Anderson classification system (Figures 2 to 5).

Figure 2: Land Use and Land Cover Map of Efon Local Government for Year 1985
Source: Image Analysis of Landsat Satellite Imagery, 2025

Figure 3: Land Use and Land Cover Map of Efon Local Government for Year 2000
Source: Image Analysis of Landsat Satellite Imagery, 2025

Figure 4: Land Use and Land Cover Map of Efon Local Government for Year 2015
Source: Image Analysis of Landsat Satellite Imagery, 2025

Figure 5: Land Use and Land Cover Map of Efon Local Government for Year 2021

Source: Image Analysis of Landsat Satellite Imagery, 2025

In discussing results, the percentage increase of Land Use and Land Cover type of the Local Government Areas was indicated with a plus sign (+) while percentage decrease was indicated with a minus sign (-), please see Table 3.

Aside percentages and area in hectares, the Change rate (Cr) is also discussed. The Cr measures the average rate of Land Use and Land Cover Change by type, per year within a given period: 1985 to 2000, 2000 to 2015 and 2015 to 2021.

Table 2: Land Use and Land Cover Area Statistics for Efon Local Government from 1985 to 2021

LULC	1985		2000		2015		2021	
	Area (ha)	%						
Built Up Area(BU)	311	1.75	407	2.29	564	3.17	795	4.47
Barren Land(BL)	2,527	14.22	3,187	17.93	2,685	15.10	2,971	16.71
Forest Land(FL)	5,635	31.70	3,905	21.97	2,481	13.96	4,134	23.26
Agricultural Land (AL)	866	4.87	4,259	23.96	5,938	33.41	2,106	11.85
Range Land(RL)	8,436	47.46	6,017	33.85	6,107	34.36	7,769	43.71
Water Body(WB)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wet Land(WL)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	17,775	100	17,775	100	17,775	100	17,775	100

Source: Image Analysis of Landsat Satellite Imagery, 2025

Table 3: Land Use and Land Cover Change Statistics for Efon Local Government from 1985 to 2021

LULC	1985-2000			2000-2015			2015-2021		
	Ca(ha)	Ce (%)	Cr (%)	Ca(ha)	Ce (%)	Cr (%)	Ca(ha)	Ce (%)	Cr (%)
Built Up Area (BU)	+96	+30.87	+1.93	+157	+38.57	+2.41	+231	+40.95	+5.85
Barren Land (BL)	+660	+26.11	+1.63	-502	-15.75	-0.98	+286	+10.65	+1.52
Forest Land (FL)	-1,730	-30.70	-1.92	-1,424	-36.47	-2.28	+1,653	+66.63	+9.52
Agricultural Land (AL)	+3,393	+391.8	+24.48	+1,679	+39.42	+2.46	-3,832	-64.53	-9.22
Range Land (RL)	-2,422	-28.71	-1.79	0	0	0	+1,662	+27.21	+3.89
Water Body (WB)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wet Land (WL)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Source: Image Analysis of Landsat Satellite Imagery, 2025

(Where Ca is Change Area, Ce is Change Extent, Cr is Change Rate and ha is Hectares)

Discussion of the results focuses more on Built Up Area (BU), Forest Land (FL) and Agricultural Land (AL) being the most significant imprint of anthropogenic activities/drivers of LULCC in the study area.

BUILT UP AREA (BU)

The results showed that between 1985 to 2021, Built Up Area (BU) increased by 60.88% from 311 to 795 hectare (Table 2) Built Up Area (BU) increased from 1.75% (311 ha) in 1985 to 2.29% (407 ha) in 2000, to 3.17% (564 ha) in 2015 and to 4.47% (795 ha) in 2021.

BU increased by average of +1.93 % per year between 1985 to 2000 but increased by average of +2.41% between 2000 and 2015, only to reduce to average growth rate of +5.85% between 2015 and 2021(Please see Cr in Table 3).

The growth rate of BU in Efon Local Government Area was fastest between 2015 and 2021 when change rate (growth rate) peaked at 5.85%.

FOREST LAND (FL)

The results showed that from 1985 to 2021, there was decline in Forest Land (FL) by 26.63% from 5,635 to 4,134 hectare (Table 2) Forest Land (FL) in area statistics showed continuous reduction from 31.70% (5,635 ha) to 21.97% (3,905 ha) to 13.96% (2,481 ha) from 1985 to 2000 to 2015 respectively but increased to 23.26% (4,134 ha) in 2021 (Table 2). The sharp increase in Forest Land (FL) between 2015 and 2021 has been largely affected by sharp decrease in Agricultural Land (AL). From the average annual change rate point of view, Forest Land (FL) declined from -1.92 % between 1985 and 2000 to -2.28% between 2000 and 2015 but increased to +9.52 % between 2015 and 2021(Table 3).

AGRICULTURAL LAND (AL)

The results showed that between 1985 to 2021 Agricultural Land (AL) increased by 58.87% from 866 to 2,106 hectare (Table 2). Agricultural Land (AL) in area statistics increased from 4.87% (866 ha) in 1985 to

23.96% (4,259 ha) in 2000, with further increase to 33.41% (5,938 ha) in 2015 but reduced to 11.85% (2,106 ha) in 2021(Table 2). From the average annual change rate point of view, Agricultural Land (AL) reduced from +24.48% growth rate between 1985 and 2000 to +2.46% between 2000 and 2015 and even further down to -9.22 % between 2015 and 2021(Table 3)

On the implications of LULCC observed in the area for planning purposes to avoid haphazard development, emphasis should be concentrated on land use planning of the settlements due to the observed increase in Built Up Area (BU). Based on previous studies, (Adegboyega, 2019; Otokiti, 2019), the study area is facing severe monstrous gully erosion caused by its steep and hilly topography and high rainfall. There is urgent need in constructing properly engineered drainage systems, reinforcing gully banks, and implementing effective development control

policies to halt construction in high-risk areas while concerted effort should be made to establish forest plantations specifically the likes of Gmelina (Gmelina arborea) and Teak (Tectona grandis), to arrest the decreasing Forest Land (FL) and Range Land (RL).

CONFUSION MATRIX

A confusion matrix (or error matrix) is usually used as the quantitative method of characterizing image classification accuracy. It is a table that shows correspondence between the classification result and a reference image. Foody (2002) recommended an 85% target for user’s, producer’s, and overall accuracies derived from the error matrix. The results of this confusion matrix showed a range from 89% to 100% which means that the image classification was accurately done. Please find below the confusion matrix for the Local Government Area for the 4 periods.

Table 4: Efon Local Government Confusion Matrix Accuracy For Year 1985

Object Id	Class Value	Predict	(BU)	(AL)	(RL)	(FL)	(BL)	Ground Truth
1	1	Built Up Area (BU)	19	0	0	0	0	19
2	19	Agricultural Land (AL)	0	14	0	0	0	14
3	32	Range Land (RL)	0	5	19	3	0	27
4	52	Forest Land (FL)	0	1	1	17	0	19
5	77	Barren Land (BL)	1	0	0	0	20	21
		Total	20	20	20	20	20	100
	Accuracy : 89%	89	89					

Source: Author’s Field Survey and Analysis 2025

Table 5: Efon Local Government Confusion Matrix Accuracy For Year 2000

Object Id	Class Value	Predict	(BU)	(AL)	(RL)	(FL)	(BL)	Ground Truth
1	1	Built Up Area (BU)	20	0	0	0	0	20
2	67	Agricultural Land (AL)	0	19	1	0	0	20
3	102	Range Land (RL)	0	0	19	0	0	19
4	154	Forest Land (FL)	0	1	0	20	0	21
5	212	Barren Land (BL)	0	0	0	0	20	20
		Total	20	20	20	20	20	100
	Accuracy:98%	98	98					

Source: Author’s Field Survey and Analysis 2025

Table 6: Efon Local Government Confusion Matrix Accuracy For Year 2015

Object Id	Class Value	Predict	(BU)	(AL)	(RL)	(FL)	(BL)	Ground Truth
1	1	Built Up Area (BU)	20	0	0	0	2	22
2	115	Agricultural Land (AL)	0	19	1	4	0	24
3	156	Range Land (RL)	0	1	19	0	0	20
4	210	Forest Land (FL)	0	0	0	16	0	16
5	269	Barren Land (BL)	0	0	0	0	18	18
		Total	20	20	20	20	20	100
	Accuracy: 92%	92	92					

Source: Author’s Field Survey and Analysis 2025

Table 7: Efon Local Government Confusion Matrix Accuracy For Year 2021

Object Id	Class Value	Predict	(BU)	(AL)	(RL)	(FL)	(BL)	Ground Truth
1	1	Built Up Area (BU)	20	0	0	0	0	20
2	155	Agricultural Land (AL)	0	20	0	0	0	20
3	207	Range Land (RL)	0	0	20	0	0	20
4	273	Forest Land (FL)	0	0	0	20	0	20
5	338	Barren Land (BL)	0	0	0	0	20	20
		Total	20	20	20	20	20	100
	Accuracy: 100%	100	100					

Source: Author’s Field Survey and Analysis 2025

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In general, the study illustrated the potentials of GIS and RS techniques to understand the characteristics and changes in Land Use and Land Cover of Efon Local Government Area of Ekiti State. The study observed that the land use characteristics evolved greatly over time and space. The creation of the Local Government Area in 1996 had remarkable effect on the growth of Built Up Area (BU), Agricultural Land (AL) and Barren Land (BL), hence the utilization of Forest Land (FL) and Range Land (RL) for development. It is remarkable that between 1985 to 2021, Built Up Area (BU) increased by 60.88%, Agricultural Land (AL) increased by 58.87% and Barren Land increased by 14.94% while Forest Land (FL) and Range Land (RL) decreased by 26.63% and 7.90% respectively.

The role of RS and GIS in this study is clearly seen as important in data collection, database development, data analysis and land use modeling for the benefit of conservation of forest resources, regional planning, and urban management. They are tools that can be used in monitoring land use changes in Efon Local Government in view of the fact that change is a continuous process. Specific recommendations are presented as follows:

1. The recently established Ekiti State Geospatial Data Centre is a welcome development. It should commence Land Use and Land Cover Change studies in the remaining fifteen Local Government areas that could not be covered in this study. The data and maps should be updated from time to time to improve land use planning by the State Government.

2. There is urgent need for land use planning, with implementation, to halt the erosion which is one of the most severe in south-western Nigeria.
3. The State Government and the Local Government Council should endeavour to focus on the Forest Land (FL) that has been on a consistent decline over the 36 years of the study. Forest Plantation projects should be encouraged across all the farm settlements in the Local Government Areas and the activities of illegal lumbering and deforestation should be discouraged.
4. The Local Government Council and the State Government should continue to encourage agriculture in the farm settlements, seeing to the security challenges by finding lasting solutions to farmers/herders conflict as well as providing farm inputs and financial support to farmers.

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COMPETITIVE INTERESTS

Author has declared that no competing interests exist.

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